

Design, Formulation And Development Of Oro-Dispersible Tablets For Pediatric Use

Rita Soyam*, Kamlesh Wadher

Department of Pharmaceutics.Smt. Kishoritai bhoyar college of pharmacy, Kamptee, Nagpur. 441002 India.

ABSTRACT

The current research work was aimed with an objective of formulation development of orodispersible tablet for pediatrics use of montelukast by using matrix former, superdisintegrants and excipient, to evaluate the effect of gelatin, superdisintegrants and their combination with excipient over physical mixture of same excipients. The sodium starch glycolate, crospovidone (as a superdisintegrants), gelatin (as a matrix former) and mannitol (as a sugar alcohol), and glycine (as a collapse protectant) were selected for formulation. The physical mixture of excipient was used to develop montelukast tablet by lyophilization method in different ratio. A lyophilized orodispersible tablet (ODT) that enhanced the in-vitro dissolution and in-vivo absorption. The developed formulation were evaluated for hardness, friability, weight variation, drug content, thickness, disintegration time, wetting time and in-vitro drug release. All batches showed weight variation within Pharmaceutical limit. Hardness was found within range of 2.96 ± 0.5 to 3.37 ± 0.2 kg/cm². Wetting time was found in between 20 ± 02 sec to 186 ± 3.51 sec. Disintegration time was found to be in between 18.5 ± 01 to 178 ± 01 sec. On the basis of this statistical analysis of data it was concluded that formulation F5 can be selected at optimized formulation after analysis of in-vitro drug release and other characteristics. The in vitro release of drug was more in formulations prepared with superdisintegrants combination and excipient in comparison to their physical mixture. The lyophilized tablet is more feasible than conventional compressed tablet, lyophilized tablet shows more patients compliance.

Keywords: Lyophilizer, Orodispersible, Montelukast, Pediatric, Superdisintegration.

INTRODUCTION

The oral route of drug administration is the most important method of administering drugs for systemic effects, except in certain cases. The topical route of administration has only recently been employed to deliver drugs to the body for systemic effect. 90% of all drugs used to provide systemic effect are administered by oral route, and solid oral dosage forms are the preferred class of product. Tablets and capsules are unit dosage forms in which the usual dose of the drug has been accurately placed. (Gupta NK et al., 2012). Tablets are solid dosage forms intended for oral administration, some of which are dissolved or dispersed in aqueous phase. Tablets are used for systemic and local drug delivery, with the drug being released from the tablet in the mouth, stomach, and intestines, and then absorbed into the systemic circulation (Kirubhashini P. et al., 2021). Orally

disintegrating tablets (ODTs), are popular amongst the young population due to several merits such as rapid disintegration, use without water, and lack of swallowing issues. (Comoglu T. et al., 2019). The various methods used to develop ODT include freeze-drying, bulk extrusion, direct compression using a superdisintegrator, tableting, etc., among which freeze-drying/lyophilization technology is a relatively recent technique. (Dalapathi Gugulothu et al., 2014). Due to the high porosity, sublimated tablets disintegrate in the oral cavity faster than other systems. A typical freeze-dried tablet consists of a drug encased in a water-soluble matrix of a hydrophilic structure-forming polymer (usually gelatin) and a filler (a saccharide - usually mannitol). Other ingredients of the tablets may be sweeteners (aspartame), taste-masking additives, and preservatives. Currently, many researchers are exploring the possibility of using other matrix-

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

forming agents in FDDF formulations. These are maltodextrins, various types of gelatin, xanthan gum, and cellulose derivatives. The type and amount of excipients have a significant effect on the characteristics of lyophilized tablets, however, the included drug can also significantly change the properties of the tablets. (Maegorzata Sznitowska et al., 2005). The quick disintegration of ODT is primarily caused by the tablet matrix's extremely porous surface. (WR Pfister et al., 2005)

MATERIAL AND METHOD: -

Materials And Components: - Montelukast Sodium was obtained from Alkem Laboratories, Mumbai, India, mannitol and Gelatine were obtained from Loba Chem, Mumbai, Microcrystalline cellulose, Sodium Starch Glycolate, and Crospovidone were obtained from Merck, India. All other reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Formulation Method Of Fdts By Lyophilization Techniques: -

In this study, FDTs containing Gelatin and Microcrystalline cellulose were prepared by lyophilization techniques according to the formulae in

Table 1. To prepare different batches, all ingredients (except gelatin and glycine) according to the formula were accurately weighed and passed through 60 and 100 mesh sieves and mixed geometrically. Gelatin was soaked in water, and hydrated gelatin was stirred onto a magnetic stirrer until a clear phase was obtained, an equal proportion of glycine, and a given amount of mannitol were added to prevent the shrinking of gelatin during manufacturing. An accurately weighed amount of Montelukast Sodium (5 mg) was dispersed in the prepared aqueous solution and stirred on a magnetic stirrer to obtain a continuous homogenous phase that resulted in a dose of 5 mg Montelukast Sodium FDTs when it was molded to 1 × 10 polyvinyl chloride (PVC) blister pack with a diameter of 13 mm and a depth of 3 mm. These fillings were kept in the deep freezer condition at -20°C for 24 h. The pre-freeze tablet mixtures were placed in a lyophilizer with a condenser temperature of 87 °C and a pressure of 0.133–0.187 mbar. The best-formulated FDTs were collected and forwarded to the next stage which involved the addition of disintegration accelerators namely, Sodium Starch Glycolate and Crospovidone to achieve an FDT with good tablet properties. (V. Dave et al., 2017)

Table 1 - The Formulation Design of Orodispersible Tablets of Montelukast Sodium

Ingredients	Formulation Batches (mg)												
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12	F13
Montelukast Sodium	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Gelatine	0.25	0.25	0.25	-	0.25	-	-	0.50	0.25	0.50	0.50	-	0.50
Glycine	8	8	8	8	-	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Mannitol	98	98	98	98	-	98	98	98	98	98	98	98	98
Microcrystalline cellulose	90	90	90	90	-	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90
Sodium starch glycolate	-	-	10	5	5	10	-	5	10	-	10	5	5
Crospovidone	-	10	-	-	5	5	5	10	10	5	5	10	-
Aspartame	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Design Of Experiment (DOE) For Fdts Of Montelukast Sodium By Lyophilization Method

In this study, Box Benken Design is used to optimize the influence of variables by Design Expert v13 software. In this design independent variables such as

(A) percent of gelatin concentration (B) percent of sodium starch glycolate concentration and (C) percent of crospovidone concentration were selected and their impact on formulation was predicted. All this dependent variable is summarized in Table 3. On behalf of this design set goals, 10 FDT formulations

were prepared and characterized for disintegration time (R1), dissolution time (R2), and drug release (R3) which were taken as a dependent variable (response parameters)

Table 2 Variables And Their Constraints In Box-Behnken Design.

Variables	Constraints	
	Lower limit	Upper limit
Independent variables		
(A) = Percent of gelatin concentration (mg)	00	0.5
(B) =percent of sodium starch glycolate concentration (mg)	00	10
(C) = percent of crospovidone concentration (mg)	00	10
Dependent variables		Goals
(R1) = disintegration time	Minimize	
(R2) = dissolution time	Minimize	
(R3) = drug release	Maximize	

Measurement Of Tablet Tensile Strength And Friability

The ability to withstand the mechanical shock of handling in manufacturing, packaging, and shipping is measured in terms of tensile strength or crushing load and friability. The crushing load for FDTs of various batches was determined by compressing the tablets in a diametric direction using a Pfizer tablet hardness tester (Cadmach, India). The friability of tablets was determined using the Roche friability USP test apparatus (Electrolab, Mumbai). Randomly six FDTs were chosen from each batch and their initial weight was determined. The FDTs were placed in a friability test apparatus and rotated at 25 rpm for 4 min. They were then removed, dusted and their final weight was determined.

The formula for calculating friability is given as Eq. (1):

$$R = \frac{W_a - W_b}{W_b} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where W_i is the initial weight and W_f is the final weight of the tablets.

Weight Variation And Tablet Thickness

Twenty tablets were randomly taken from each batch and their average weight was determined. The

individual tablet was taken and its weight was calculated. That individual weight was compared with the average weight. The weights were measured using a weighing balance. Twenty tablets were randomly selected from formulations and thickness was measured individually by screw gauge. The results were expressed in millimeters.

Measurement Of Disintegration Time

The in-vitro disintegration time of formulated FDTs was determined using a digital disintegration apparatus (Electrolab, Mumbai, India) using 900 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer at 37 ± 0.5 °C. Six tablets from each batch were randomly chosen and the average time for complete disintegration of these tablets was determined Table. All FDTs under test took 16–170sec to disintegrate completely. This quick disintegration time was achieved as a result of using the lyophilization technique.

Wetting Time And Water Absorption Ratio

To determine the wetting time of FDTs, a piece of tissue paper was taken and it was folded twice, and placed in a culture dish ($d = 6.5$ cm) containing about 6 ml of purified water. An FDT having a small amount of amaranth powder on the upper surface was placed on tissue paper. The time elapsed in developing red color on the upper surface of the FDTs was

determined and noted. To determine the water absorption ratio, the wetted tablets were transferred to a tissue paper wiped off any excess water, and weighed immediately. Results are presented in Table 3. The water absorption ratio was calculated by following the formula given in Eq. (2):

$$R = \frac{W_a - W_b}{W_b} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where W_b is the weight of the tablet before the study and W_a is the weight of the tablet after the study

Drug Content Of Lyophilized FDTS

Three tablets were randomly chosen from each batch, crushed and the blend equivalent to 5.0 mg of montelukast sodium was accurately weighed and transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask. Phosphate buffer (pH 6.8), 20 ml was added under continuous stirring, and volume was made up to 100 ml with the

same. The solutions were filtered and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 280nm. Measurements were performed in triplicates.

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy

FTIR studies of montelukast sodium and admixture were carried out using FTIR spectrometer (Bruker, Alpha, US) over the range 2,000 to 400 cm^{-1} and a resolution of 1 cm^{-1} after 57 scans, with standard KBr beam splitter. Place approximately 2 mg montelukast sodium on powder keep anvil in the up position so that it covers the powder. Gently press down on the anvil till it contact with sample. If necessary, rotate the anvil arm to ensure full contact is made with the powder. (Kuldeep Kumar et al. 2019) FTIR Spectroscopy is perform to know the compatibility and interactions. The FTIR spectra are shown in (Fig. 1). The FTIR study did not show any possible interaction between montelukast sodium and other excipients used in the fast-dissolving tablets.

Table 3 - Evaluation Of Orodispersible Tablet Of Montelukast Sodium.

Batch	Hardness (Kg/Cm ²)	Friability (%)	Thickness (Mm)	Wetting Time (Sec)	Water Absorption Ratio	Weight Variation
F1	3±0.3	0.71±1.2	4.45±0.2	75±1	28±0.012	199.85±0.6
F2	2.8±0.9	0.71±2.1	4.62±0.3	69±1	26±0.001	198.25±0.42 50.4
F3	2.5±0.1	0.63±0.6	4.62±0.3	75±2	49±0.019	200.64±1.66
F4	2±0.5	0.64±3.1	4.01±0.4	65±1	32±0.003	200.57±1.79
F5	2.9±0.35	0.53±1.1	5.12±0.35	70±2	29.3±0.0199	201.70±1.33 ±1.33
F6	2.1±0.24	0.64±1.2	4.89±0.4	74±2	43.1±0.009	201.12±2.23
F7	2±0.2	0.68±2.0	4.68±0.2	60±1	20±0.001	201.44±1.50
F8	3±0.45	0.57±0.2	5.58±0.5	74±3	30.9±0.019	200.71±1.81 ±1.85
F9	2.9±0.65	0.63±1.1	4.95±0.67	72±3	31.5±0.018	200.94±1.45
F10	2.32±0.5	0.51±1.0	4.86±0.35	78±3	36.3±0.005	200.99±0.9
F11	3.56±0.8	0.56±0.5	5.39±0.4	85±4	49.6±0.019	199.92±1.02
F12	2±0.33	0.72±0.2	4.79±0.72	76±3	35±0.013	199.89±1.30
F13	3.23±0.72	0.54±1.5	4.95±0.4	78±3	45.5±0.015	200.30±2.19

Fig 1: -FT-IR Spectra Of The Physical Mixture And Montelukast Sodium

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron microscopy was used to determine the morphological appearance of the formulated FDTs. The coating of FDTs was done using gold for 10 min with the use of a fine-coat ion-sputter and examined under FE-SEM. Signals of electron-sample interactions reveal information about the sample including crystalline structure, chemical composition, external morphology, etc. A variety of signals at the surface of solid specimens were recorded (Fig. 2). The data was collected from FDTs and 2-dimensional images were generated that displayed spatial variations in these properties.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

The thermal behavior of montelukast sodium was conducted on a DSC- 3 STARe system (METLER TOLEDO) at a heating rate of 10°C/min from 30 to 200°C under the nitrogen purge gas flow rate of 50 mL/min. Pure water and indium were used as primary standard for the instrument for temperature and heat flow using the DSC temperature scale and enthalpy response as standard. Montelukast sodium pure drug about 6 mg were packed in an indium-sealed pan which were then subsequently crimped to ensure a tight seal and measured under a nitrogen atmosphere. (Ullah F et al., 2022).

Drug Content

Randomly, two tablets were chosen from each batch, crushed, triturated and the blend powder equivalent to 10 mg of montelukast sodium in the formulation was dissolved in water and made it 10 ml. The further suitable dilutions were made with phosphate buffer

pH 6.8 and the concentration of the drug was analysed using UV visible spectrophotometer at 280 nm.

In-Vitro Drug Release Studies

The in-vitro dissolution studies of the formulated FDTs were studied in USP dissolution apparatus type II (Tab Machines, Mumbai, India) with a paddle stirrer at 100 rpm filled with 900 ml pH 6.8 phosphate buffer at 37 ± 0.5 °C. FDTs were placed in a basket and the program was set for five minutes. Aliquots of dissolution media (2 ml) were withdrawn initially and after every 1 min and replaced with fresh dissolution media. The samples were filtered through a 0.45µ filter membrane (Millipore, County Cork, Ireland) and absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically at λ_{max} 261 nm. The dissolution test was carried out in triplicate and is presented in (Fig 4)

Response Surface Methodology

Response surface methodology (RSM) has proved to be a useful statistical and mathematical technique in modeling and process optimization of experimental variables which influences relevant responses and the objective of this research is to optimize these responses. RSM explores the relationships between several independent variables (factors) and one or more dependent variables (responses). This design is very flexible and suitable for modeling possible curvature in the response functions and constructing second-order polynomial models moreover a third level for a continuous factor facilitates investigation of the quadratic relationship between the response and each of the factors. Ten FDT formulations were prepared and the effect of independent variables on responses (dependent factors) was evaluated using RSM and is presented in (Fig). Three independent

variables were selected: the concentration of Gelatin (X1); the concentration of sodium starch glycolate (X2), and the concentration of crospovidone(X3) and each variable was tested at different concentrations, the quantities of which are expressed in their respective units. The responses evaluated were: disintegration time (R1), dissolution time (R2), and

drug release (R3). Experiments were performed according to a randomized procedure and the scheme showing the values of process variables corresponding to the observed responses is reported in Table. Design expert V.15 software was used for the generation and evaluation of response surf

Fig. 2(A), (B): - FE-SEM Micrograph Of Formulated Oro-Dispersible Tablet

Fig 3: - DSC Of Formulation

Fig 4 – Graph Of % Drug Release Per Minute Of Fast

Table 4 – Process Variables And Their Responses

Batch	Disintegration time (sec)	Dispersion time (sec)	Drug content (%)	Drug Release (%)
F1	150.9±4.5	155.1±5.9	89.99±1.5	95±0.8
F2	19.1±2.1	19.2±1.0	91.71±1.67	99.5±0.5
F3	141.5±3.9	145.1±4.9	89.75±1.52	87±1.5
F4	120.9±3.5	122.3±4.6	88.99±1.31	88±0.6
F5	20±2.2	21.4±1.0	90.89±1.75	99.89±1.0
F6	40±2.5	41.3±3.0	90.41±0.96	89±1.8
F7	18.5±1.5	18.5±1.0	93.51±1.43	98.73±1.0
F8	41±2.1	40.4±2.5	90.70±1.89	89±1.0
F9	34.1±2.5	33.6±2.0	90.80±0.45	99±1.2
F10	73.5±4.2	75.45±3.2	89.52±1.23	87±1.5
F11	60.6±4.8	61.2±3.0	90.01±0.55	88±1.0
F12	25±3.2	24.9±2.1	90.57± 0.20	99±0.3
F13	170.6±4.2	173.95±5.3	89.90± 1.48	84±0.2

Fig 5 - Response Surface Plot Showing Effect Of Concentration Of Gelatin, Crospovidone, And Sodium Starch Glycolate On A), B), C) Disintegration Time; D), E), F) Dissolution Time; And G), H), I) % Drug Release.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION: -

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

FTIR spectra of montelukast sodium are shown in Figure 1. According to the Figure, stretching region of hydroxyl group, O-H was showed at the band range of 3200-3600 cm^{-1} . The band at 3371.33 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of hydroxyl group in the montelukast sodium. The band for carbonyl group (C-O) peaks appeared at the band at 1710 cm^{-1} . FTIR spectrum of montelukast sodium exhibited the absorption peaks 2359.18 and 2997.33 cm^{-1} assigned to C-H, C \equiv C stretching respectively. The results were found to be concurrent with a reference spectrum of montelukast sodium. (Kuldeep Kumar et al. 2019) The observation of the infrared spectroscopy (IR) spectra of physical mixture of montelukast sodium and excipients (Fig.1) showed all the major peaks of the montelukast sodium, indicating that there was no interaction between the montelukast sodium and excipients. FTIR spectra of montelukast sodium, and physical mixture (montelukast sodium+gelatin+SSG+CP) shown in figure 1 respectively.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry

The results of thermal analysis using DSC carried out at temperature of 30-250°C with a heating rate of 10° C/min showed a shift in the endothermic peak temperature and enthalpy of montelukast sodium. The thermogram of montelukast sodium showed a broader peak, due to amorphous nature of drug, its melt between 46.4 – 103.5 °C. The melting point peak indicate at 74.9 °C of drug as shown in Figure 3 (Ullah F. et al., 2022). Physical mixture of montelukast sodium orodispersible tablet (montelukast sodium+excipients) showed intense endothermic peak at 165.0°C. The thermogram of physical mixture of montelukast sodium orodispersible tablet (montelukast sodium+excipients) has a clear, sharp, endothermic peak of excipient while the endotherm of montelukast sodium disappeared. The disappearance of peak and change in the thermal property of montelukast sodium in the physical mixture and might be attributed to complete mixed and solubilization or molecular dissolution of the drug with excipients.

Field Emission Scanning Microscopy (FESEM)

The morphology of prepared orodispersible tablet was determined by FESEM and photomicrographs of orodispersible tablet are displayed in fig. 2. The surface morphology observed by the FESEM showed the pores formed, and the matrix structure of higher level of gelatine concentration of the prepared orodispersible tablet. The resultant orodispersible tablet did not show any rough on the surface, validating its rapid clearing from the oral cavity with a good deposition pattern in the oral cavity.

Drug Content (%)

The drug content varied from 84.22 \pm 1.52 % to 95.34 \pm 1.43 % as shown in table 6.20. Among all the formulations, F7 has shown greater drug content and the lowest one obtained was in the case of F3. All values are expressed as mean \pm SD, n=3, SD: standard deviation.

In-Vitro Drug Dissolution Studies

The release profile of the orodispersible tablets (batch F1 to F13) was carried out separately as shown in table 4. Montelukast Sodium orodispersible tablet showed drug release in a range between 84.02 \pm 3.8 to 99.89 \pm 3.5 at 15 min with the highest % drug release obtained for batch F5 and the lowest one obtained in the case of batch F13. The release behavior of montelukast sodium orodispersible tablet shows a pattern of triphasic drug release in Figure 4 an initial burst release in the first followed by a small plateau and lastly a higher released effect. Since the drug is hygroscopic it dissolution through a phosphate buffer core showing a higher release. However, the order of drug release is inversely proportional to the superdisintegrants and gelatine content which again highlights the dispersion role in dissolution. Since the higher superdisintegrants content dispersion of the orodispersible tablet, it also restricts the amount of drug released outside the tablet. However, it has been established that the incorporation of gelatine increases the stability of orodispersible tablets.

Experimental Design and Analysis

The results of regression analysis for responses R1, R2, and R3 were obtained and fit to the quadratic model. The regression equation of the fitted quadratic

model for the R1, R2, and R3 responses were as follows-

$$R1 = + 126.375 + 32.50*A - 3.225*B - 31.70 *C - 7.0*AB - 6.80*AC + 0.240*BC + 214.0*A^2 + 0.415*B^2 + 2.065*C^2$$

..... (1)

$$R2 = + 10.92917 - 10.483 *A + 0.06083 *B - 2.02167*C - 0.10 *AB - 0.20 *AC + 0.028 *BC + 36.067*A^2 - 0.00183*B^2 + 0.117167*C^2$$

..... (2)

$$R3 = + 93.24542 + 32.86167*A - 0.8417*B + 1.5083 *C + 2.146 *AB - 1.20*AC + 0.075*BC -$$

$$101.913*A^2 - 0.049783*B^2 - 0.077083*C^2$$

..... (3)

The response surface plots representing the relationship between the studied factors and measured responses are demonstrated in (Figure 5)

Stability Studies

Stability Studies were done on montelukast sodium orodispersible tablets according to ICH guidelines. A minimum quantity of tablets in glass bottles was stored in a stability chamber at 25°C/60%RH±5% and the samples were checked at 0 to 60 days. The results indicated that there was no significant change in tablet properties.

Table - 5 Stability Studies

Sr. no.	Parameters	Initial	Time (Days)	
			30 Days	60 Days
1.	Appearance	White color tablet	No change	No change
2.	Disintegration	20 sec	Results were found same	Approximately 20 sec
3.	Dissolution	99%	No change	Approximately 99%

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The best dosage forms are solid ones, such as pills and capsules. 90% of medications are delivered orally, which makes it essential for systemic effects. For both local and systemic medication delivery, tablets, and capsules are unit dose forms with a 20–50% mistake rate. Orodispersible pills are popular among active people and those with swallowing difficulty since they dissolve fast in the mouth and are great for coughing and motion sickness. Fast-dissolving tablets are preferred by pediatric and elderly patients due to their quick absorption and minimal adverse effects, which makes them perfect for travel. The term "Orodispersible tablets," which refers to mouth-dissolving tablets, is becoming more and more common in business.

The trial's goal was to develop a pediatric orodispersible tablet that would decrease the frequency of doses and increase patient adherence to a daily dose of montelukast sodium.

Leukotriene receptor antagonists like montelukast sodium are used to treat and manage asthma. Gelatine, sodium starch glycolate, and crospovidone are added to orodispersible tablets ranging from 0.50 mg to 10 mg.

The study looks into the usage of crospovidone and sodium starch glycolate as superdisintegrants in orodispersible tablets. It finds that these agents' concentrations can be increased to increase disintegration time and in-vitro drug release, which in turn can improve the mechanical strength of the tablet. Physical characteristics such as hardness, friability, weight variation, and sodium content of montelukast were assessed for each formulation in the study. The last batch, batch F5, which contained crospovidone, sodium starch glycolate, and gelatine, was thought to be optimal because of its rapid drug release and short disintegration time.

The study developed stable, safe, and fast-release Orodispersible tablets of Montelukast Sodium for rapid therapeutic action. 13 formulations were optimized

using Sodium Starch Glycollate and Crospovidone as super disintegrants. The formulation (F5) showed a maximum of 99.89% drug release at 4 minutes and showed no significant changes at different storage conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We are very thankful to the management of Smt. Kishoritai Bhojar College of Pharmacy, Kamptee, Nagpur, for providing the necessary facilities and encouragement.

REFERENCES

1. Abd Elbary A, Ali AA, Aboud HM. Enhanced dissolution of meloxicam from orodispersible tablets prepared by different methods. Bulletin of Faculty of Pharmacy, Cairo University. 2012 Dec 1;50(2):89-97.
2. Aarti J, Sonali J, Ganesh D. Orodispersible tablets: A comprehensive review. Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology. 2014 Mar 1;7(3):8.
3. Arora P, Sethi VA. Orodispersible tablets: A comprehensive review. Int J Res Dev Pharm Life Sci. 2013 Feb;2(2):270-84.
4. Bandari S, Mittapalli RK, Gannu R. Orodispersible tablets: An overview. Asian Journal of Pharmaceutics (AJP). 2008;2(1).
5. Comoglu T, Dilek Ozyilmaz E. Orally disintegrating tablets and orally disintegrating mini tablets—novel dosage forms for pediatric use. Pharmaceutical Development and technology. 2019 Aug 9;24(7):902- 14.
6. Dave V, Yadav RB, Ahuja R, Yadav S. Formulation design and optimization of novel fast dissolving tablet of chlorpheniramine maleate by using lyophilization techniques. Bulletin of Faculty of Pharmacy, Cairo University. 2017 Jun 1;55(1):31-9.
7. Dey P, Maiti S. Orodispersible tablets: A new trend in drug delivery. Journal of natural science, biology, and medicine. 2010 Jul;1(1):2.
8. Ghosh T, Ghosh A, Prasad D. A review on new generation orodispersible tablets and its future prospective. International journal of pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences. 2011 Jan;3(1):1-7.
9. Gupta, Maram Suresh, Tegginamath Pramod Kumar, Devegowda Vishkante Gowda, and Jessica M. Rosenholm. "Orodispersible films: Conception to quality by design." Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews 178 (2021): 113983.
10. Gupta DK, Maurya A, Varshney MM. Orodispersible tablets: An overview of formulation and technology. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences. 2020 Aug 13;9(10):1406-18.
11. Heer D, Aggarwal G, Kumar SH. Recent trends of fast dissolving drug delivery system—an overview of formulation technology. Pharmacophore. 2013 Jan 1;4(1):1-9.
12. Jain D, Amul M. A review-formulation & development of orodispersible tablet. IJPE. 2014 May;4:21-38.
13. Jassem NA. Orodispersible Tablets: A Review on Recent Trends in Drug Delivery. Journal of Drug Delivery Technology. 2022;12(1):432-6.
14. Kavitha, - (2013) Formulation and Evaluation of Montelukast Sodium Chewabletablets by Direct Compression Method. Masters thesis, J.K.K. Natraja College of Pharmacy, Komarapalayam.
15. Kirubhashini P. Formulation Development and Evaluation of OroDispensible Tablets of Levosalbutamol (Doctoral dissertation, The Erode College of Pharmacy and Research Institute, Erode). (2021)
16. Kumar RS, Ghosh A. FAST DISSOLVING TABLETS: PATIENT COMPLIANCE DOSAGE FORMS.
17. Mohapatra S, Kar P, Singh S, Nayak BS, Mishra SR. Orodispersible Tablets: An approach for drug delivery in buccal cavity.
18. Mohire NC, Yadav AV, Gaikwad VK. Novel approaches in development of metronidazole orodispersible tablets. Research journal of pharmacy and technology. 2009;2(2):283-6.
19. Nagar P, Singh K, Chauhan I, Verma M, Yasir M, Khan A, Sharma R, Gupta N. Orally disintegrating tablets: formulation, preparation techniques and evaluation. Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science. 2011 Jun 30(Issue):35-45.
20. Naresh Kumar G. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Montelukast Sodium Chewable Tablets (Doctoral dissertation, KK College of Pharmacy, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India). (2012)
21. Nilesh Chindhu P. Formulation and Evaluation of Orodispersible Tablets of Metoclopramide

- Hydrochloride (Doctoral dissertation, Nandha College of Pharmacy, Erode, Tamilnadu, India.)
22. Patil AV, Sali DH, Reddi SS, Wargade NS, Mohaptra SK, Paygude BV. Recent trends and formulation technology of orodispersible tablets. *Journal of Pharmacy Research*. 2011 Mar;4(3):924-8.
 23. Patil PB, More VN, Tour NS. Recent trends in orodispersible tablets—An overview of formulation technology and future prospects. *International Journal of Pharma Sciences and Research*. 2015;6(7):1056-66.
 24. Rakesh Pahwa, Mona Piplani, Prabodh C. Sharma, Dhirender Kaushik and Sanju Nanda; Orally Disintegrating Tablets - friendly to pediatrics and geriatrics: Scholars research library archives of applied science research 2010, vol. 2 (2): 35-48
 25. Rewar S, Singh CJ, Bansal BK, Pareek R, Sharma AK. Oral dispersible tablets: An overview; development, technologies and evaluation. *International Journal of Research and Development in Pharmacy & Life Sciences*. 2014 Nov 15;3(6):1245-57.
 26. Sharma MC, Leel M. A Review: Oral Dispersible Tablets. *Int J Drug Dev & Res*. 2022;14(1).
 27. Singh K, Saroha K, Mohan R, Kumar A, Pandit C. Orodispersible tablets: Development, technologies and evaluation: An overview. *The pharma Research*;8(1):128-47.
 28. Sudhir Bhardwaj, Vinay Jain, R.C. Jat, Ashish Mangal, Suman Jain; Orally Disintegrating Tablets: Drug invention today 2010, vol. 2 (2): 81-88.
 29. Tejvir K, Bhawandeep G, sandeep K. Mouth Dissolving Tablets: A novel approach to drug delivery. *Int J Curr Pharm Res*, 2011; 3: 1-7
 30. Ullah F, Shah KU, Shah SU, Nawaz A, Nawaz T, Khan KA, Alserihi RF, Tayeb HH, Tabrez S, Alfatama M. Synthesis, characterization and in vitro evaluation of chitosan nanoparticles physically admixed with lactose microspheres for pulmonary delivery of montelukast. *Polymers*. 2022 Aug 29;14(17):3564
 31. Rita S, Keshav H, Swati M, Dnyaneshwar M, Kamlesh W, Millind U; Advancements in Orodispersible Tablet Formulations: A Comprehensive Review of Novel Technologies and Emerging Trends 2023 Sep, vol. 8 (9):216-234.

HOW TO CITE: Rita Soyam, Kamlesh Wadher, Design, Formulation And Development Of Oro-Dispersible Tablets For Pediatric Use, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (6), 176-186. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20579473>

